

Prevalence of Overweight and Obesity and its Associated Risk Factors and Complications among School Children (10_14) Years

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Abstract: Background: The rising prevalence of childhood obesity and overweight has become a significant public health concern, given the increased likelihood of these children developing chronic non-communicable diseases in the future.

Aim: This study contributed to ascertain the prevalence of obesity and its associated complications and risk factors among schoolchildren.

Patients and methods: The study was conducted in a sample of public and private mixed-gender educational establishments in different hospitals in Iraq. The sample consisted of 77 schools for children between the ages of 10 and 14 years, and the research was carried out between June 2023 and October 2024. Those who were overweight or obese were identified using the body mass index (weight in kg/height in m²). A standardised instrument was prepared and administered to collect information on the socio-demographics and different risks to which the respondent was exposed.

Results: The current study findings indicate that the prevalence of overweight and obesity was 38.96% and 61.04% in males and females, respectively, across both government and private schools. Additionally, children who watched ≥ 4 hours of television per day exhibited 55 cases, while children who engaged in physical activity for 3 days per week demonstrated 56 cases. Furthermore, 54 cases were observed for children who consumed junk food or fast food ≤ 4 days per week. The following risk factors were identified in the course of our study: family history of obesity (relative risk [RR] 1.67, 95% confidence interval [CI] 0.54–8.77), consumption of junk or fast food (RR 1.50, 95% CI

1.31–1.85), socioeconomic factors (RR 1.04, 95% CI 0.73–2.25), and watching television and eating food simultaneously (RR 4.38, 95% CI 2.72–6.94).

Conclusions: The study revealed that children from middle-class backgrounds with limited access to outdoor activities and a tendency to consume junk or fast food were more susceptible to becoming overweight or obese in Iraq.

Key words: Overweight; Obesity; Schoolchildren; Complications; and Risk factors.

Introduction

In addition to environmental influences related to lifestyle choices, obesity is a complicated illness with a hereditary tendency [1]. The incidence of overweight and obesity, which affects adults as well as kids and adolescents, has increased to the point that it may be regarded as a serious public health problem despite the presence of several prevention strategies [2,3,4,5]. Over the past 20 years, there has been a significant increase in the incidence of obesity, mostly as a result of eating pattern alterations, lifestyle modifications, decreased physical activity, as well as economic access [6,7]. Since 1980, obesity has been more common worldwide; in 2015, 39% of persons (18 years of age and older) were overweight. Six hundred million (13%) of them were obese [8,9,10,11]. Overweight and obesity were far more prevalent among Latin America along with the Caribbean than they are worldwide. About 350 million people, or 58% of the population, were overweight in 2018; 145 million individuals, or 25% of the population, were obese [12,13,14]. Globally, the incidence of childhood overweight and obesity has risen, raising serious public health concerns. Children, as well as young people, are affected by the worldwide epidemic in overweight and obesity [15]. In 2020, more than 40 million children aged 0 to 5 were considered fat, and almost 20% of school-aged children were overweight or obese, according to worldwide figures released by the World Health Organization. [16]

Patients and methods

The study included 77 urban schoolchildren from both government and private schools in different hospitals in Iraq. In this regard, all government and private schools were randomly selected from the list available in the respective hospitals between June 2023 and October 2024. A total of 77 children, aged between 10 and 14 years, were selected as the study population in accordance with the pre-established inclusion criteria through the application of simple random sampling. In developing the research tool, consideration was given to the study's objectives, which included the collection of demographic data, an evaluation of obesity, and an assessment of associated odds. The reliability coefficient ($r = 0.95$) was also determined.

Following approval by the school authority, all children in the appropriate age group underwent assessments of weight, height, and BMI estimation. A pre-prepared questionnaire was administered to the study participants in order to ascertain the risk factor-associated characteristics of the households and individuals within the representative sample. Consequently, the respective class teachers were requested to oversee the screening activities for their respective classes.

One useful and trustworthy indicator of obesity is the body mass index or BMI. It is computed by dividing the weight of a person in kilograms by the square of their height in meters (kg/m^2). The body mass index, or BMI, may be computed simply by dividing the height in meters squared (height in 2 meters) by the weight in kilograms. In this case, a BMI for age chart was used to assess overweight and obesity for children and adolescents. Children were categorized as overweight if their body mass index (BMI) was among 22.0 and 25.9 kg/m^2 and obese if their BMI was higher than 25.9 kg/m^2 .

A univariate analysis was performed with a 95% level of confidence to determine the association between risk variables and overweight/obesity in individuals. The following were the requirements for inclusion: (a) acceptance of participants in the study who are between the ages of 10 and 14; and (b) preparedness and desire to participate and help. Children who were underweight and reluctant to engage, as well as those older than 14, were excluded. The acquired data was analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results

Table 1 showed the demographic characteristics of the study population, comprising 43 males and 34 females. The prevalence of overweight and obesity was 38.96% and 61.04% in males and females, respectively. Malnutrition was observed in 75.32% of patients. School type was classified into two categories: government schools (59.74%) and private schools (40.26%). Socioeconomic status was categorized into three groups: upper class (21 cases), middle class (41 cases), and lower class (15 cases).

Table 1. Baseline of features in children's patients.

Variables	No. of Patients, 77	Percentage, %
Age	12.5 ± 1.5	
Sex, M/F		
Male	43	55.84%
Female	34	44.16%
BMI, Kg/m ²		
Overweight	30	38.96%
Obesity	47	61.04%
Malnutrition		
Yes	58	75.32%
No	19	24.68%
School type		
Government	46	59.74%
Private	31	40.26%
Father occupation		
Working	63	81.82%
Not – working	14	18.18%
Mother Occupation		
Working	25	32.47%
Housewife	52	67.53%
Socio – economic status		
Upper class	21	27.27%
Middle class	41	53.25%
Lower class	15	19.48%

The results demonstrated that children in school with ≤ 4 hours of TV watching time per day exhibited 22 cases, while those with ≥ 4 hours of TV viewing time per day demonstrated 55 cases. Additionally, 56 cases were observed for children engaging in physical activity and play for 3 days per week, followed by 15 cases for those engaging in these activities for 4–6 days per week. Furthermore, 54 cases were observed for children consuming junk food or fast food ≤ 4 days per week, while 15 cases were observed for those consuming these foods 4–7 days per week, which these results were defined in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Distribution of physical activity data on children's school.

Factors	No. of Patients, 77	Percentage, %
Watching TV Time (hr/day)		
< 4	22	28.57%
≥ 4	55	71.43%
Time of playing and physical activity (days/week)		
3	56	72.73%
4 – 6	15	19.48%
Seven dailies	6	7.79%
Junk food/ fast food (days/week)		
< 4	54	70.13%
4 – 7	15	19.48%
Every day	8	10.39%

It constructed complications prevalent in children in the long term, where the most common factor was dyslipidemia with 20 cases, followed by high blood pressure with 14 cases, and sleep apnea with 13 cases., where all outcomes were identified in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Distribution of complications related to children with obesity in the long term.

Complications	No. of Patients, 77	Percentage, %
Type 2 diabetes	9	11.69%
High blood pressure	14	18.18%
Dyslipidemia	20	25.97%
High cholesterol	10	12.99%
Sleep apnea	13	16.88%
Depression and anxiety	11	14.29%

In **Table 4**, we performed a univariate analysis on children school with overweight and obesity in determining of risk factors related to children. It shows that each of the factors listed down in Table 4, where the most factors found Family history of obesity with 1.67 [0.54 – 8.77], Use of junk or fast food with 1.50 [1.31 – 1.85], Socioeconomic factors with 1.04 [0.73 – 2.25], Watching TV and eat food with 4.38 [2.72 – 6.94].

Table 4. Analysis outcomes of risk factors related to obese children.

Items	OR and CI 95% value
Family history of obesity	1.67 [0.54 – 8.77]
Use of junk or fast food	1.50 [1.31 – 1.85]
Watching TV and eat food	4.38 [2.72 – 6.94]
Skipped snacks	2.13 [0.70 – 5.34]
Practice daily activity	1.04 [0.57 – 5.89]
Socioeconomic factors	1.04 [0.73 – 2.25]
Psychological factors	2.78 [0.16 – 3.80]
Dyslipidemia	1.015 [0.06 -1.56]
High cholesterol	4.03 [0.65 – 5.88]

Discussion

In developing nations like Iraq, it is critical to recognize the risk factors linked to childhood obesity and excess weight. It was discovered that 38.96% and 61.04% of the study population, respectively, were overweight or obese. These numbers are consistent with those found in previous research [17,18], such as one that found that 24% and 8% of North German urban kids were overweight and obese, respectively.

According to a different population-based cross-sectional survey, 7.5 percent of kids in Pakistan were obese, and 17 percent were overweight in 2020 [19]. Middle-class children are more likely to be overweight or obese than children in many other nations, including those with high and poor incomes. [20]

The gender-based disparities among weight distribution patterns are reflected in the much greater rate of overweight and obesity in men (55.84%) compared to women (44.16%). The results of earlier research carried out in other developing nations are consistent with this conclusion.

Similarly, the research conducted by Dutch [21] scholars also revealed that in cases where mothers have received an education, a higher percentage of them are employed as a consequence of them spending less time monitoring their children's physical activity or sedentary behaviours, such as television viewing. Furthermore, working mothers are more likely to provide their children with foods that are high in energy density, such as junk and fast foods. This contributes to an increased risk of obesity and overweight, as these foods significantly elevate BMI. [22,23,24]

According to the study's findings, students who attended private schools are more probable than those who attend public schools to be overweight or obese. The frequency of both overweight and obesity was shown to be significantly correlated with children's comparatively greater socioeconomic position [25]. [26] Children who ate junk food or fast food and was less physically active were more likely to be overweight or obese. This is probably due to the perception that lifestyle changes that led to the intake of foods low in nutrients, as well as a lack of physical exercise, were important factors in the rate in overweight and obesity in the community being studied. [27, 28, 29]

Conclusions

The prevalence of overweight and obesity among schoolchildren in Iraq prior to the onset of the study is a cause for concern. The prevalence of overweight and obese children is high, at 38.96% and 61.04%, respectively. The prevalence of overweight and obesity is higher among males than females. Furthermore, a correlation was identified between television viewing and weight gain. The more television watched, the greater the weight gain. This highlights the necessity for increased health awareness and motivation among all stakeholders to in still healthy habits in children with urgency. Implementing functional health and nutrition education programs alongside promoting outdoor recreation for children in schools represents a crucial primary preventive measure.

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